

Evaluating FAIRness of Genomic Databases

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Abstract. Several studies show the difficulty experienced for the reuse of the ever-increasing amount of genomic data. Initiatives are being created to mitigate this concern; one of the most well-known is the FAIR Data Principles. Nonetheless, the related works are too generic and do not describe simultaneously and properly the human and machine perspectives of the FAIRness of databases. Hence, in order to bridge this gap, our paper introduces an approach named the Bio FAIR Evaluator Framework, a semi-automated tool aimed to analyze the FAIRness of genomic databases. Furthermore, we performed experiments that analyzed selected genomic databases according to two orthogonal and complementary perspectives (human and machine). The approach uses standardized FAIR metrics and generates recommendation reports to researchers indicating how to enhance the FAIRness of databases. Our findings, when compared with related works, show the feasibility of the approach, indicating that the current genomic databases are poorly compliant with FAIR Principles.

Keywords: Genomics, Data Compliance, FAIRness, FAIR.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, the ever-increasing volume of research data is widely debated in the scientific fields. Today, managing, sharing, and reusing scientific data are among the main issues addressed by the research community, mainly because of the complexity and lack of general governance rules [1, 2]. One of the areas facing these problems is bioinformatics, and, more specifically, genomics, which is concerned with the study of genes and their function, applying the techniques of genetics and molecular biology to the genetic mapping sequencing of sets of genes or the complete genomes of selected organisms. The results are organized in databases, with rich applications in medicine, pharmaceutical industry, and biology, among others [3].

Genomics is in the midst of a datacentric revolution, which is causing an escalation in the size and number of genomic datasets [4]. Many archives, as highlighted by [5], are hard to be found, shared, or reused due to the lack of precise semantics and provenance. These problems are like those addressed by the FAIR data principles [6] introduced in 2016 [6]. The FAIR principles (and their 15 sub principles) were stated as goals aiming to provide guidelines for creating digital resources such as datasets, databases, code, workflows, and research objects, in a way that makes them (F)indable,

(A)ccessible, (I)nteroperable, and (R)eusable, strongly relying on metadata publication and management.

However, the sole existence of the FAIR principles is not enough to aid the researcher in evaluating the FAIRness of genomic databases. We advocate that it should be conducted under two orthogonal and complementary perspectives (human and machine) because humans and machines deal with distinct obstacles when attempting to find and access data on the databases [6]. As far as we are concerned, the human perspective is about the upper level of abstraction and the diffuse sense of “semantics”. Humans can identify and interpret a wide variety of signs and make intuitive decisions on the selection of useful data. On the other hand, the machine perspective is more self-guided, accurate, and even more reproducible. It concentrates on the ability to evaluate data in the scope, scale, and speed necessity that the genomic research requires [6].

In this work, we evaluated the FAIRness of seven well known genomic databases, analyzing how close these databases are to achieve FAIRness. To do that, we developed a semi-automated tool named Bio FAIR Evaluator Framework to support researchers to evaluate the databases, considering metrics and criteria based on the interpretation of the FAIR principles. Furthermore, we discuss the tool usage performing two sets of experiments and analyses focused on the orthogonal perspectives mentioned above. Besides, our tool additionally offers a series of recommendations about the improvements that can be made in the genomic databases.

This article is structured as follows: section 2 presents the background of the genomic databases and FAIR principles; in section 3 we present the core features our contribution named Bio FAIR Evaluator Framework; section 4 presents the two sets of complementary experiments and its results, showing the FAIRness of the database according to the two perspectives; section 5 shows the related works; and, finally, section 6 presents concluding remarks and topics for further investigation.

2 Background

2.1 Genomic Databases

Most genomic datasets are derived from legacy sequencing projects which are frequently openly accessible to the public. This practice is evidenced by the fact that most journals require a public accession identifier for any dataset associated with a publication. Thus, to attain a broad distribution of open datasets, all subfields of genomics have also adopted the use of central, large-scale public databases [7].

The early adoption of these databases to host large amounts of all sorts of genetic data has allowed researchers to efficiently query data and promote reuse datasets produced by others [7, 9]. Genbank¹, EBI², UniProt³, and KEGG⁴ are some of the most

¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>

² <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/>

³ <https://www.uniprot.org/>

⁴ <https://www.genome.jp/kegg/>

well-known databases in the area. However, they represent a small part of a group of more than 1,364 databases linked to the life sciences area [10]. Many of these archives are highly consolidated and have a long history, but it is also highly recognized in the academy that these same databases present issues of the most varied types [5, 11-13].

When analyzing in-depth these concerns, several inconsistencies in data and metadata are evident. In some cases, there is a lack of control in the (meta)data vocabularies, reduced use of semantic-related concepts, and even simple fields are filled with different data [13]. It is noticeable that these problems are closely addressed by the FAIR principles, where reuse is one of the main target goals. It is also natural that some of those works cite FAIR as a potential for circumventing these problems.

2.2 FAIR Principles and FAIRness

Sharing and reusing research data is not an easy task. Considering the researchers' point of view, data preservation is a critical role that supports data reuse. Data reuse can be executed either by humans or machines (a.k.a data reusers), which need time and resources to understand the data to identify whether it has value to be reused in a given context [8]. Reuse by some means focuses on the ability to understand the reuser perspective, but the main question ends up being how the data is stored, how the data producers classified it, or even how the data archive presents their data [1].

The problem of reusability is being worsened by the escalating volume of ever-increasing genomic data being produced worldwide even before the COVID-19 pandemics. To mitigate the reuse problem, in 2016, the FAIR data principles were established by Wilkinson et al. [6]. A set of stakeholders devised these principles to stress the role of Open Science with a focus on the '(meta)data', where the authors use this term in cases that must be applied to metadata and data [6]. The FAIR principles are composed of 15 sub principles (See Fig. 1), where each of these goals aims to maximize the value of digital research objects either for humans or machines.

<p>Findable</p> <p>F1 (Meta)data with globally unique and persistent identifier.</p> <p>F2 Data with rich metadata.</p> <p>F3 Metadata with data identifier.</p> <p>F4 (Meta)data indexed in a searchable resource.</p>	<p>Accessible</p> <p>A1 Use a standardized communication protocol.</p> <p>A1.1 Use an open, free and universally protocol.</p> <p>A1.2 The protocol allows authentication and authorization.</p> <p>A2 Metadata accessible, even with no available data.</p>
<p>Interoperable</p> <p>I1 (Meta)data use formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.</p> <p>I2 (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles.</p> <p>I3 Use of qualified reference in (meta)data.</p>	<p>Reusable</p> <p>R1 Metadata need to be detailed.</p> <p>R1.1 Clear and accessible data usage license.</p> <p>R1.2 Use of detailed provenance.</p> <p>R1.3 (Meta)data are approved by domain-relevant community standards.</p>

Fig. 1. The FAIR Data Principles

The FAIRness of digital resources (like a genomic database) is the degree to which it is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable not only in the Web, but in other contexts as well. Thus, increasing the FAIRness of a genomic database might maximize their reuse. Nevertheless, to evaluate its FAIRness, we need to use metrics (a.k.a criteria) to obtain an assessment that provides feedback to content creators about the resulting degree of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. This means that genomic communities should not only understand how to access the genomic data

stored in these databases but also be aware that they can monitor the FAIRness of these databases, realistically and quantitatively.

3 **Bio FAIR Evaluator Framework**

After conducting a systematic review of the literature (not discussed in this paper due to lack of space), it has been perceived that there were no computational frameworks that aid researchers in evaluating genomic databases considering the FAIR principles according to these two orthogonal perspectives (human and machine).

We aim to contribute with the Bio FAIR Evaluator framework. Differently from previous works, described in section 5, it is a semi-automated modular tool that helps scientists to check the FAIRness of databases by walking through assessments related to each of the four groups of FAIR principles [14]. The framework is composed of two self-contained and independent modules: Researcher Compliance Evaluator (RaCE) and Machine Compliance Evaluator (MaCE). RaCE is related to the human perspective; it holds a list of questions related to the process of genomic data discovery and reuse. A researcher performs the RaCE by manually answering each question based on the human perspective using pre-specified reference criteria in order to delve into the FAIRness conformity. MaCE is a Python script that dynamically loads a set of pre-establish questions that were automatically answered after checking the genomic database to evaluate the FAIRness of the database.

The evaluation of the FAIRness of the databases is achieved through the execution of both modules; they check the structure of the genomic databases using several metrics (criteria) to assess compliance with each one of the FAIR sub-principles of the genomic databases.

We stress that our approach allowed us to evaluate databases FAIRness through compliance experiments according to the two orthogonal perspectives. In short, the compliance experiments represent an evaluation considering either scenarios involving humans or machines regarding the acceptance of data reuse from autonomous computer applications. Our metrics, evaluation criteria, and experiments are described in the following subsections, and all reports created to carry out this analysis are available in a GitHub repository⁵.

3.1 **Metrics and Criteria of FAIRness evaluation**

The development of the framework allowed us to test the alignment of genomic databases with FAIR principles. Hence, we outlined standardized metrics to generate quantitative outputs considering the execution of compliance experiments with the assistance of RaCe and MaCE modules.

For the sake of clarity, the traffic-light colour system was chosen to categorize the scores of the two modules. We use four levels: green for exemplary databases that meet the compliance criteria (score = 3), yellow for average databases that partially meet the

⁵ doi:10.5281/zenodo.3949344

criteria (score = 2), red for poor databases that not meet the criteria (score = 1) and grey for cases that cannot be tested (score = 0). Extra attention is deserved to MaCE because the output of the script returns two types of results: green for databases that meet the criteria (score = 3) and red for those that do not meet (score = 1).

To structure the criteria, we scrutinized previous genomics analyses databases works [5, 11, 12], and also the FAIRsharing⁶ and re3data⁷ portals, in order to extract what is a trustworthy genomic database according to RaCE and MaCE. We developed the three levels of criteria that focus on how close a genomic database is to FAIR principles and linked to the metric score already described. The metrics and criteria aided then the reinforcement of the recommendation stage that is presented after the evaluation.

3.2 RaCE Module

RaCE module aims to analyze the databases considering human needs, for example, the necessities during the search of a use license or finding the last release of a (meta)data, taking as a starting point the 15 FAIR sub principles. By this, each principle is analyzed and linked with the necessities of the genomic data human reuser.

The questions of RaCE can be subdivided into two modules: the first one describes the module and its relation to the FAIR principles; the second is a set of precondition steps to be taken during the evaluation and a follow-up questionnaire linked to the aforementioned metrics and criteria.

3.3 MaCE Module

The MaCE module focuses on analyses according to a machine perspective. Differently from RaCE that uses only manual assessments, it was necessary to develop a computational environment explicitly focused on this scenario. The automated module was elaborated following previous research [13], where the FAIR principles are extended to machine vision-oriented maturity indicators called FAIR Metrics Gen2 (FM-Gen2). We adopted the same metrics, proposed by the FAIR principles developers, which will be included and discussed during the presentation of the results.

To support MaCE module, we developed Python scripts, based on the objectives of each FM-Gen2 metric, and also reformulated some of them in the view of genomic databases analysis, to evaluate genomics specific concerns and better understand the outputs results. Correspondingly to the description of the RaCE module, we developed the same analysis structure in MaCE. First, describing the module and the relation to FAIR, outlining the precondition steps, how the module should be analyzed considering the metrics and criteria, and how the support script will execute the evaluation.

⁶ <https://fairsharing.org/>

⁷ <https://www.re3data.org/>

4 Results and discussion

To evaluate the FAIRness of the genomic databases, we designed and executed experiments with RaCE and MaCE. Both considered seven popular resources widely adopted by the genomics community.

The requirements for choosing these databases and repositories were to be the most representative in the genomics area and consider the use of the FAIR principles in their (meta)data. The evaluated databases were: Genbank (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/), KEGG (www.genome.jp), EBI (www.ebi.ac.uk), UniProt/Swiss-Prot (www.uniprot.org), EuPathDB (www.eupathdb.org), VirusDB (www.viprbrc.org) and MaizeGDB (www.maizegdb.com). On the follow-up section, the results of FAIRness experiments are grouped by the FAIR principle related name, as cited on Fig. 1, in addition, the MaCE receive the FM-Gen2 acronym cited before. All experimental data, tables, statistics, and graphs, accompanied by the documentation, can be accessed via the GitHub repository⁵.

4.1 FAIRness Experiments

The (F)indable RaCE module was the first executed. As a result, most of the data holdings met the requirements criteria (Fig. 2 (a)). Despite that, the F2 experiment has the most non-exemplary databases; this module evaluates if data is richly described with metadata, and perhaps this can be considered a subjective principle. Nonetheless, it is noticeable that the same databases have in common the absence of required fields or the use of incoherent/incorrect metadata.

In turn, the MaCE module (Fig. 2 (b)) have higher compliance rates concentrated on FM-Gen2 F1.1 and F4 analysis. FM-Gen2 F1.1 evaluates if there are any unique identifiers in the databases, as a Uniform Resource Identifier (URI). FM-Gen 2 F1.2 and F1.3 experiments identify the existence of standardization in persistence identifiers and obtained a result below 42.86% for poor databases. For instance, the guarantee of persistence is a problematic point for all FAIR principles; its use adds greater control and reusability over (meta)data. Interestingly, Genbank had lower results on these modules, which substantiates previous findings in the literature [5, 12].

Fig. 2. Findable module results

FM-Gen2 F2.1 and F2.2 appraise the identification of structured language related to richly described metadata accessed by machines, and obtained 57.14% of poor databases, because they do not use a standardized structured language. Besides, FM-Gen2

F3.1 and F3.2 found the lowest compliance rate in the (F)indable MaCE module, only around 28.57% as exemplary. These evaluations refer to the explicit use of identifiers in metadata about the data and for other metadata. Consequently, non-compliance generates an obstacle for scraping data tools. However, the FM-Gen2 F4 performs the search for the (meta)data on search engines, and only one database was poor, as it does not authorize search engines to perform scraping.

Fig. 3. Accessible module results

With the (A)ccessible RaCE module, the databases achieved 100% compliance on A1, A1.1, and A1.2 (see Fig. 2 (a)). This result occurred because these experiments search for the use of standardized communication protocols and the use of non-proprietary software. A2 RaCE experiment obtained 42.86% of average or poor databases due to the non-use or non-specification of policies for persistence/versioning of (meta)data. The results of (A)ccessible MaCE module (see Fig. 2 (b)) ended up being satisfactory in the FM-Gen2 A1.1.1, A1.1.2, A2.1.1, and A2.1.2 with 85.71% of compliance, checking if they use open free protocols and if there are authentication/authorization for access (meta)data. However, FM-Gen2 A2 revealed that all databases are non-compliant to the existence of persistence policy keys.

The most remarkable compliance rate was in (I)nteroperable module, RaCE compliance was below 42.86% (Fig 3 (a)), mainly in I2 experiment, where the (meta)data vocabularies must follow the FAIR principles. Even the data holdings that cite the use of FAIR also failed this test. Regarding I1 and I3 experiments, non-compliance comes from not using knowledge representation languages and qualified references.

Fig. 4. Interoperable module results

Correspondingly, the same scenario is noticeable in the MaCE, with 100% of non-compliance in FM-Gen2 I2.2, because the databases do not use linked data on metadata. Nevertheless, FM-Gen2 I1.1 had 85.71% of compliance. It verifies if metadata uses

knowledge representation in the most basic form, using any type of structured data, being readily accepted even for HTML. Conversely, FM-Gen2 II.2 has greater rigor in the analysis where only knowledge representation languages are accepted.

Fig. 5. Reusable module results

On the reusable module, general non-compliance is seen. In RaCE, two points stand out, and the first is R1.1, where 100% were average. Referring to the use of licenses, some databases contained the license. However, they were not complete or were hard to find. The second highlighted is the R1.3 experiment, where there is a need for certification by the data domain community. Even creating criteria for analysis, there are no documents yet or FAIR guidelines that assist this. Likewise, MaCE experiments obtained non-compliance between 57.14% and 85.71% due to the non-indexing of user licenses for automatic identification. In addition to that, there are no experiments for R1.2 and R1.3 FAIR principles because it is hard to measure from the machine point of view.

The results of RaCE and MaCE experiments were grouped to analyze compliance in general (See Fig. 5). This is because, as mentioned before, we are dealing with two complementary and orthogonal perspectives.

Database	RaCE	MaCE	Final Average
Genbank	33	34	34.5
KEGG	38	52	46
EBI	38	52	46
UniProt	41	54	48.5
EuPathDB	26	28	28
VirusDB	31	36	34.5
MaizeGDB	38	46	43

Fig. 6. Final Compliance Result of the Seven Genomic Databases

By this final results, interesting points can be highlighted. From the three with the highest score, only UniProt mentions the use of FAIR principles in its (meta)data. On the other hand, MaizeGDB cites the use of FAIR but ended up being the fourth in compliance. Genbank is one of the most popular genomic databases. However, it is the one that has smaller compliance with the FAIR principles.

4.2 Recommendations

After the analysis was carried out, a referenced document⁵ was made with possible recommendations that could be made for each compliance experiment's results. Among

the most important recommendations, one can cite the use of persistent identifiers, the use of knowledge representation languages, and the provision of policies for the (meta)data.

These three points can be summarized as the main improvements of following the FAIR principles. Some end up being simpler to be implemented, such as the provision of policies for the use of (meta)data. Although the use of knowledge representation languages, turn out to be even more complicated in existing databases due to the need to readapt all (meta)data to the chosen language. We should not see the FAIR as a guide that must be followed thoroughly [14], but reaching all the principles can generate many benefits. However, non-completeness does not result in an 'unFAIR' database. FAIRness must be adapted in each of the realities but the principles can certainly improve reusability. Based on the compliance recommendations, it is possible to make the principles more concrete.

5 Related Work

There are some works aimed at evaluating compliance concerning the FAIR principles. Dunning, Smale, and Bohmer [16], clearly inspired our work, as they proposed a series of compliance experiments on the FAIR principles, although focused on different areas. They perform experiments from a human point of view and quoted that some of the principles are too vague. At the same time, others are more complicated to verify adherence, especially Interoperable and Reusable.

The FM-Gen2 [15] is very important as providing a view on the analysis focused on machines, due to its automatic reuse. However, it ends up not carrying out experiments on all principles, such as principles R1.2 and R1.3. The Research Data Alliance [17] gathered and compared 12 FAIR analysis tools, contemplating compliance indicators. During these analyses, the tools were grouped, considering the different FAIR principles. Comparing these tools, we noticed some interesting facts. Some have restrictions to use, in others not all the principles were analyzed (like principle A2 that was only analyzed by three tools). Some tools contemplate either the human vision or the machine vision.

All these works were essential to the development of our research, but mainly the FM-Gen2 that we used on our compliance experiments. Different from the related works, we focus on the compliance of a specific area, make compliance experiments to map all the FAIR principles, and ended up providing analysis from two points of view (human and machine).

6 Conclusions

Reusability of genomic data is utterly necessary. However, several databases face various types of shortcomings related to FAIRness. In this investigation, we presented an approach to evaluate the genomic databases, considering two orthogonal perspectives (human and machine). Bio FAIR Evaluator Framework allows researchers to perform complementary manual and automated experiments to evaluate FAIRness of genomic

databases. Our results show that seven of them are poorly compliant with the FAIR principles. Besides the compliance checks, the evaluation also generated a series of recommendations to increase the FAIRness of genomic databases. Our framework may also benefit data reusers and database administrators. As future work, we intend to develop further investigations to improve the quality of compliance experiments to evaluate other fields of bioinformatics like proteomics as well as other domains.

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